

Research Article

Design of RC Series-Parallel Oscillator Circuit

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Abstract: To produce a large range of audio frequencies especially to produce sinusoidal oscillation in signal generator RC series parallel oscillator plays a major role. Sinusoidal oscillation is constituted of four parts: amplifier circuit, frequency selection network, positive feedback circuit and amplitude stabilization link. The principle is that when the DC power supply is turned off, the frequency reaches the interference signal string and enters the input terminal of the oscillation circuit, and appears at the output terminal of the circuit after amplification. But due to the small amplitude and frequency mixing, they are not the output signals we are looking for. After the signal passes through the frequency selection and positive feedback network, a frequency signal shields other signals, suppresses it and returns to the input end of the amplifier circuit. The circuit loop gain should be slightly greater than 3 to obtain the desired result. This continuous periodic amplification results in distortion of the output signal, and the final image chain can output a sine wave with a fixed frequency, amplitude, and stability.

Keywords: Oscillator, Sinusoidal Oscillation, Wein-Bridge Oscillator, RC Oscillator, RC Series-Parallel Circuit.

Introduction

An oscillator generates output without any AC input signal. This is a circuit which converts DC energy into AC at a very high frequency. They are designed to deliver waveforms as well, e.g. square, triangle, and saw-tooth waveforms, if intended for applications in wireless radio

communications, the sinusoidal waveform is probably the most important one. A good sinusoidal oscillator is expected to deliver either a voltage or a current signal that is stable both in amplitude and frequency. Because a variety of oscillator structures are available that are suitable for generation of sinusoidal waveforms, circuit designers make the choice mostly based on their personal preference for one particular type of oscillators.

Figure 1: Oscillator Block Diagrams.

Classifications

Electronic oscillators are classified mainly into the following two categories –

- Sinusoidal Oscillators –The oscillators that produce an output having a sine waveform are called sinusoidal or harmonic oscillators. Such oscillators can provide output at frequencies ranging from 20 Hz to 1 GHz.
- Non-sinusoidal Oscillators –The oscillators that produce an output having a square, rectangular or saw-tooth waveform are called non-sinusoidal or relaxation oscillators. Such oscillators can provide output at frequencies ranging from 0 Hz to 20 MHz.

Forms of Sinusoidal Oscillators:

We will discuss only about Sinusoidal Oscillators. Sinusoidal oscillators can be classified in the following categories:

- Tuned Circuit Oscillators –These oscillators use a tuned-circuit consisting of inductors (L) and capacitors (C) and are used to generate high-frequency signals. Thus they are also

known as radio frequency R.F. oscillators. Such oscillators are Hartley, Colpitts, Clapp oscillators etc.

- RC Oscillators – These oscillators use resistors and capacitors and are used to generate low or audio-frequency signals. Thus they are also known as audio-frequency (A.F.) oscillators. Such oscillators are Phase –shift and Wein-bridge oscillators.
- Crystal Oscillators –These oscillators use quartz crystals and are used to generate highly stabilized output signal with frequencies up to 10MHz. The piezo oscillator is an example of a crystal oscillator.
- Negative-resistance Oscillator –These oscillators use negative resistance characteristic of the devices such as tunnel devices. A tuned diode oscillator is an example of a negative-resistance oscillator.

Oscillation Nature:

The nature of oscillations in a sinusoidal wave is generally of two types. They are damped and undamped oscillations. Damped oscillation is the electrical oscillations whose amplitude goes on decreasing with time are called as Damped Oscillations. The frequency of the damped oscillations may remain constant depending upon the circuit parameters. This generally produced by the oscillatory circuits that produce power losses and doesn't compensate if required. Undamped oscillation is the electrical oscillations whose amplitude remains constant with time are called as Undamped Oscillations. The frequency of the undamped oscillations remains constant.

Figure 2: Oscillation Natures.

In an ideal circuit, where there are no losses, the oscillations would continue indefinitely. In a practical tank circuit, there occur losses such as resistive and radiation losses in the coil and dielectric losses in the capacitor. These losses result in damped oscillations.

RC Oscillator:

We are given to work with only RC oscillator where there will be a series and parallel connection of composed parts of the circuit.

Feedback Fractions and Stages

As we know they also called Audio frequency oscillators and examples as Phase shift and Wein Bridge oscillators. RC Oscillators use a combination of an amplifier and an RC network to produce oscillations due to the phase shift between the stages. For an oscillator to sustain oscillations indefinitely, sufficient feedback of the correct phase that is 'Positive Feedback' must be provided along with the transistor amplifier being used acting as an inverting stage to achieve this.

Figure 3: RC Feedback Fraction.

In an RC Oscillator circuit the input is shifted 180degree through the amplifier stage and 180degree again through a second inverting stage giving us '180 + 180 = 360' of phase shift which is effectively the same as '0' thereby giving us the required positive feedback. In other words, the phase shift of the feedback loop should be '0'.

The three RC stages are cascaded together to get the required slope for a stable oscillation frequency. The feedback loop phase shift is -180degree when the phase shift of each stage is -60o. This occurs when $\omega = 2\pi f = 1.732/RC$ as ($\tan 60o = 1.732$). Then to achieve the required phase shift in an RC oscillator circuit is to use multiple RC phase-shifting networks such as the circuit above.

In a Resistance-Capacitance Oscillator or simply an RC Oscillator, we make use of the fact that a phase shift occurs between the input to a RC network and the output from the same network by using RC elements in the feedback branch for example;

Figure 4: RC Phase Shift & Stages.

The circuit on the left shows a single resistor-capacitor network whose output voltage ‘leads’ the input voltage by some angle less than 90o. An ideal single-pole RC circuit would produce a phase shift of exactly 90o, and because 180o of phase shift is required for oscillation, at least two single-poles must be used in an RC oscillator design.

Basic RC Oscillator:

The Phase –shift oscillator is called the BASIC RC OSCILLATOR which produces a sine wave output signal using regenerative feedback obtained from the resistor-capacitor combination. This regenerative feedback from the RC network is due to the ability of the capacitor to store an electric charge.

Figure 5: Basic RC Oscillator.

This resistor-capacitor feedback network can be connected as shown above to produce a leading phase shift (phase advance network) or interchanged to produce a lagging phase shift (phase retard network) the outcome is still the same as the sine wave oscillations only occur at the frequency at which the overall phase-shift is 360 degree. By varying one or more of the resistors or capacitors in the phase-shift network, the frequency can be varied and generally this is done by keeping the resistors the same and using a 3-ganged variable capacitor. The loading effect of the amplifier on the feedback network has an effect on the frequency of oscillations and can cause the oscillator frequency to be up to 25% higher than calculated. Then the feedback network should be driven from a high impedance output source and fed into a low impedance load such as a common emitter transistor amplifier but better still is to use an operational Amplifier as it satisfies these conditions perfectly.

Operational Amplifier:

Operational Amplifier RC Oscillators are more common than their bipolar transistors counterparts. The oscillator circuit consists of a negative-gain operational amplifier and a three section RC network that produces the 180 degree phase shift. The phase shift network is connected from the op-amps output back to its 'inverting' input as shown below.

Figure 6: Op-Amp RC phase Shift Oscillator.

As the feedback is connected to the inverting input, the operational amplifier is therefore connected in its ‘inverting amplifier’ configuration which produces the required 180degree phase shift while the RC network produces the other 180degree phase shift at the required frequency (180 + 180) degree. Although it is possible to cascade together only two single-pole RC stages to provide the required 180degree of phase shift (90+ 90)degree, the stability of the oscillator at low frequencies is generally poor.

One of the most important features of an RC Oscillator is its frequency stability which is its ability to provide a constant frequency sine wave output under varying load conditions. By cascading three or even four RC stages together (4 x 45) degree, the stability of the oscillator can be greatly improved. RC Oscillators with four stages are generally used because commonly available operational amplifiers come in quad IC packages so designing a 4-stage oscillator with 45degree of phase shift relative to each other is relatively easy. RC Oscillators are stable and provide a well-shaped sine wave output with the frequency being proportional to 1/RC and therefore, a wider frequency range is possible when using a variable capacitor. However, RC Oscillators are restricted to frequency applications because of their bandwidth limitations to produce the desired phase shift at high frequencies.

Phase Shift and Gain

The Wien Bridge oscillator is a two-stage RC coupled amplifier circuit that has good stability at its resonant frequency, low distortion and is very easy to tune making it a popular circuit as an

audio frequency oscillator but the phase shift of the output signal is considerably different from the previous phase shift RC Oscillator. The Wien Bridge Oscillator uses a feedback circuit consisting of a series RC circuit connected with a parallel RC of the same component values producing a phase delay or phase advance circuit depending upon the frequency. At the resonant frequency f_r the phase shift is 0 degree.

Consider the circuit below;

Figure 7: Wein Bridge RC Network.

The above RC network consists of a series RC circuit connected to a parallel RC forming basically a High Pass Filter connected to a Low Pass Filter producing a very selective second-order frequency dependant Band Pass Filter with a high Q factor at the selected frequency. At low frequencies the reactance of the series capacitor (C_1) is very high so acts a bit like an open circuit, blocking any input signal at V_{in} resulting in virtually no output signal, V_{out} . Likewise, at high frequencies, the reactance of the parallel capacitor (C_2) becomes very low, so this parallel connected capacitor acts a bit like a short circuit across the output, so again there is no output signal. So there must be a frequency point between these two extremes of C_1 being open-circuited and C_2 being short-circuited where the output voltage, V_{OUT} reaches its maximum value. The frequency value of the input waveform at which this happens is called the oscillators Resonant Frequency. At this resonant frequency, the circuits reactance equals its resistance and the phase difference between the input and output equals zero degrees. The magnitude of the output voltage is therefore at its maximum and is equal to one third ($1/3$) of the input voltage as shown;

Figure 8: Oscillator Output Gain and Phase Shift

It can be seen that at very low frequencies the phase angle between the input and output signals is ‘Positive’ (Phase Advanced) while at very high frequencies the phase angle becomes ‘Negative’ (Phase Delay). In the middle of these two points the circuit is at its resonant frequency with the two signals being ‘in-phase’ or zero degree. We can therefore define this resonant frequency point with the following expression.

$$f_r = \frac{1}{2\pi RC}$$

where f_r is the Resonant Frequency in Hertz, R is the Resistance in Ohms, C is the Capacitance in Farads.

Figure 9: Wein-Bridge Oscillator

The output of the operational amplifier is fed back to both the inputs of the amplifier. One part of the feedback signal is connected to the inverting input terminal (negative or degenerative feedback) via the resistor divider network of R1 and R2 which allows the amplifiers voltage gain to be adjusted within narrow limits. The other part, which forms the series and parallel combinations of R and C forms the feedback network and are fed back to the non-inverting input terminal (positive or regenerative feedback) via the RC Wien Bridge network and it is this positive feedback combination that gives rise to the oscillation.

The RC network is connected in the positive feedback path of the amplifier and has zero phase shift at just one frequency. Then at the selected resonant frequency, (f_r) the voltages applied to the inverting and non-inverting inputs will be equal and 'in-phase' so the positive feedback will cancel out the negative feedback signal causing the circuit to oscillate. The voltage gain of the amplifier circuit MUST be equal to or greater than three "Gain = 3" for oscillations to start because as we have seen above, the input is 1/3 of the output. This value, ($A_v \geq 3$) is set by the feedback resistor network, R1 and R2 and for a non-inverting amplifier this is given as the ratio $1+(R1/R2)$. Also, due to the open-loop gain limitations of operational amplifiers, frequencies above 1MHz are unachievable without the use of special high frequency op-amps.

Wien Bridge Oscillator Frequency

From the previous discussion the magnitude of the output voltage, V_{out} from the RC network is at its maximum value and equal to one third ($1/3$) of the input voltage, V_{in} to allow for oscillations to occur. But why one third and not some other value. In order to understand why the output from the RC circuit above needs to be one-third that is $0.333 \times V_{in}$, we have to consider the complex impedance ($Z = R \pm jX$) of the two connected RC circuits.

We know from our AC Theory tutorials that the real part of the complex impedance is the resistance, R while the imaginary part is the reactance, (X). As we are dealing with capacitors here, the reactance part will be capacitive reactance, (X_c).

Figure 10: Impedances of RC Network

The RC network as shown, we can clearly see that it consists of two RC circuits connected together with the output taken from their junction. Resistor R_1 and capacitor C_1 form the top series network, while resistor R_2 and capacitor C_2 form the bottom parallel network.

Therefore the total DC impedance of the series combination (R_1C_1) we can call, Z_S and the total impedance of the parallel combination (R_2C_2) we can call, Z_P . As Z_S and Z_P are effectively connected together in series across the input, V_{IN} , they form a voltage divider network with the output taken from across Z_P as shown.

Noted that for the lower parallel impedance (Z_p), as the two components are in parallel, we have to treat this differently because the impedance of the parallel circuit is influenced by this parallel combination. The magnitude of the output voltage, V_{out} will be equal to $(Z_{out} \times V_{in})$ which as shown is equal to one third ($1/3$) of the input voltage, V_{in} and it is this frequency selective RC network which forms the basis of the Wien Bridge Oscillator circuit. If we now place this RC network across a non-inverting amplifier which has a gain of $1+R_1/R_2$ the following basic Wien bridge oscillator circuit is produced.

Materials and methods

Now we will design two circuit one with Transistor and another with Operational op-amp and judge which is giving us more accurate results with less difficulties.

First Circuit Experiment

Wien Bridge Oscillator is one of the most common type of oscillators used in audio and sub-audio frequency ranges (20 – 20 kHz). This type of oscillator is simple in design, compact in size, and remarkably stable in its frequency output. Furthermore, its output is relatively free from distortion and its frequency can be varied easily. However, the maximum frequency output of a typical Wien bridge oscillator is only about 1 MHz. This is also, in fact, a phase-shift oscillator. It employs two transistors, each producing a phase shift of 180° , and thus producing a total phase-shift of 360° or 0° .

Required Components:

- *2N3904 NPN Transistor (2)*
- *Capacitors 1 μ 0 Farad(1), 10 μ Farad(1), 33n Farad (2)*
- *Resistors 27k ohm(1), 4k7 ohm(3), 39k ohm(1), 1k0 ohm(1), 22k ohm(1), 3k3 ohm(1)*
- *Potentiometer 1k0 ohm (1)*

Figure 11: Oscillator Using Transistors.

It is essentially a two-stage amplifier with an R-C bridge circuit. R-C bridge circuit (Wien Bridge) is a lead-lag network. The phase-shift across the network lags with increasing frequency and leads with decreasing frequency. By adding Wien-bridge feedback network, the oscillator becomes sensitive to a signal of only one particular frequency. This particular frequency is that at which Wien bridge is balanced and for which the phase shift is 0° . If the Wien-bridge feedback network is not employed and output of transistor Q_2 is feedback to transistor Q_1 for providing regeneration required for producing oscillations, the transistor Q_1 will amplify signals over a wide range of frequencies and thus direct coupling would result in poor frequency stability. Thus by employing Wien-bridge feedback network frequency stability is increased.

This bridge circuit can be used as feedback network for an oscillator, provided that the phase shift through the amplifier is zero. This requisite condition is achieved by using a two stage amplifier, as illustrated in the figure. In this arrangement the output of the second stage is

supplied back to the feedback network and the voltage across the parallel combination $C_2 R_2$ is fed to the input of the first stage. Transistor Q_1 serves as an oscillator and amplifier whereas the transistor Q_2 as an inverter to cause a phase shift of 180° . The circuit uses positive and negative feedbacks.

And, the circuit which I used while launching my project is a simple fixed frequency wein bridge oscillator in which Q_1 and Q_2 are both wired as low-gain common-emitter amplifiers. Q_2 gives a voltage gain slightly greater than unity and uses Wien network resistor R_1 as its collector load and Q_1 presents high input impedance to the output of the Wien network and has its gain variable via RV_1 . The component values show that the circuit oscillates at about 1 kHz — in use, RV_1 should be adjusted so that a slightly distorted sine wave output is generated.

Figure 12: Output Waveforms of Fig11.

We can easily observe the values of the amplitude and the frequency from the oscilloscope simulation of the circuit.

As you can see, the screen of the oscilloscope has 5 divisions on the vertical axis. We know that $V/Div = 1.25 V$. So;

Amplitude = $5 \times 1.25 = 6.25$ V (Peak-to-Peak)

We also can calculate the frequency by the formula that we explained previously.

“The output signal of the circuit is not a proper sin wave, so after analyzing the circuit we have found that we need to tune the potentiometer carefully to get the proper gain to oscillate proper sin wave, if we tune the potentiometer carefully to get the proper gain then we will definitely get the proper sin wave”

Advantages of this circuit:

1. Provides a stable low distortion sinusoidal output over a wide range of frequency.
2. The frequency range can be selected simply by using decade resistance boxes.
3. The frequency of oscillation can be easily varied by varying capacitances C1 and C2 simultaneously. The overall gain is high because of two transistors.

This circuit also has some disadvantages

Disadvantages of this circuit:

1. The circuit needs two transistors and a large number of other components.
2. The maximum frequency output is limited because of amplitude and the phase-shift characteristics of amplifier.

Second Circuit Experiment

Keeping the first circuit's benefits and disadvantages in mind, we tried to design another circuit with much less components and more efficient. So this time we use op-amp instead of transistor.

Even though when Wien bridge oscillators were first created by Max Wien in 1891 used a lamp in the circuit, today there are many variations that can be done instead but that create the same output. Back during that time, lamps were used often. Today they aren't used as much. This is why there have been modifications to the original circuit design that was created by Mr. Wien.

So in this circuit we're going to use a variation. We don't have to use a lamp, because today it's not very common to use lamps anymore. And you may not have it. If you do, of course you can use it. But in place of a lamp, we can substitute a resistor.

So to build this circuit, all you need is an UA741 op amp and resistors, capacitors, and potentiometers. Potentiometers are variable resistors which allow us to adjust the gain of the circuit.

Through the resistor and capacitor values we choose, we can determine the frequency and gain of the output sine wave signal.

And If we want make the oscillation steady, and then we need to add Diodes in our circuit. So in our 2nd simulation we tried to design a circuit using diodes with a UA 741 Op-Amp and tried to get as accurate sin wave as we can.

Components Needed

- UA741 Op Amp
- 3 resistors
- 2 15K Ω resistors, and 10 nF ceramic capacitors (RC series parallel network)
- 2 Diodes “1N914”
- 10K Ω potentiometer

UA741 Op Amp is a single package Op-Amp that has been widely used by engineers and students for quite a long time now. This Op-Amp can be used for many general purpose applications like, Voltage follower, Buffers, Comparators, Amplifiers, Adders and much more. So if you looking for a plain old Op-Amp just for some basic circuit design then this IC might be the right choice for you.

Wien Bridge Oscillator Circuit Built with an UA741:

We will have these kind of advantages while building this oscillator Advantages

- Distortion testing of power amplifier.
- It supplies the signals for testing filters.
- Excitation for AC Bridge.
- To fabricate pure tune.

- Long distance can be spanned by the resting beams.

The Wien bridge oscillator circuit that we will build with an UA741 is shown below:

Figure 13: Oscillator Using Op-Amp(741)

It consists of an operational amplifier 741 and two diodes, and of course a Wien bridge composed of resistors R_3 , R_4 and capacitors C_1 and C_2 . When the gain is greater than 3, the Op-Amp amplifier starts. This is achieved by variable resistance VR1. When it moves to the left, at a certain value, the gain is greater than 3, and the op-amp begins to provide the signal in a rectangular form. After that, I should reduce the value of VR_1 - to the maximum right so that the signal can become a sinusoidal signal.

Two diodes provide a stable gain (for a stable sinusoidal signal, it should always be $g = 3$), if gain ($G = 3$) diode is turned off. When the voltage is positive, D1 is turned on and R5 is connected in parallel, which reduces g to 3. Conversely, when the voltage is negative, D2 is

turned on and R6 is connected in parallel. So the gain drops to 3. This ensures a stable sinusoidal signal.

Here G stands for voltage Gain

- ❖ If $G = 3$, oscillations occur
- ❖ If $G < 3$, oscillations attenuate
- ❖ If $G > 3$, oscillation diminish

“Adding a diode network to keep circuit around $G = 3$, If $G = 3$, diodes are off

When output voltage is positive, D1 turns on and R4 is switched in parallel causing G to drop

When output voltage is negative, D2 turns on and R4 is switched in parallel causing G to drop”

With the use of diodes, the non-ideal op-amp can produce steady oscillations.

Frequency Analysis:

By changing the resistor and capacitor values in the positive feedback network, the output frequency can be changed.

The measurement formula of frequency is as follows: $f = 1/2 * \pi * r * c$, $R = R3 = R4 = 15k$, $C = C1 = C3 = 10nF$, frequency is $106 \text{ Hz} \sim 1\text{kHz}$. So if we want, we can change the value according to our needs. It is important to note that this amplifier provides a stable signal until the frequency reaches 1 MHz. At the output end, we have placed a voltage divider with resistors R7 and R8, due to the fact that $-45\text{dbm} = 0.0044\text{V}$ at resistance 600 ohms.

So the final result can be seen on the oscilloscope. Yellow sinusoids are provided by Wien Bridge, and blue sinusoids are generated by sinusoidal generators with the same characteristics and integrated into software .we think it is ideal without any noise and distortion. There is an offset at a voltage of only 2 mV, so we think it is very satisfactory.

Figure 14: Output Waveform of fig 13.

Conclusion

In order for us to test the circuit with slightly different values of resistors and to allow us to gain Control over the output frequency we tweaked the final circuit in the following manner:

- We added a low pass filter at the end of the circuit to further smooth out the wave.
- We added 1K potentiometers in series with the existing ones in frequency selective network for gaining control over the output frequency.

A project Test was setup by connecting the +V and -V to variable +V supply and variable -V Supply respectively. As we increased or decreased +V, keeping the -V constant, the positive slope of the output increased or decreased respectively. On the other hand, as we increased or

decreased $-V$, keeping the $+V$ constant, the negative slope of the output increased or decreased respectively.

The result we concluded was, as we change the supply voltage of the op-amp, the frequency changes.

And as the difference between $|+V|$ and $|-V|$ increased, distortion became more prominent.

According to our judgement we can conclude as, the circuit with the diodes is more stable, less distorted. That's why we choose this circuit as our project circuit.

Finally the staff come in conclusion that what we have really learned making this designed circuit;

- No Input Signal yet Produces Output Oscillations
- Amplifier gain should be above 3 for an oscillation to happen.
- Distortion happens if the input voltages ($-V$ and $+V$) are not equal.
- Can Output a Large Range of Frequencies
- With Proper Configuration and tuning , Oscillations can go on indefinitely
- Oscillators made up of Op Amp are usually limited to the lesser end of the frequency spectrum, mainly due to the reason that they do not possess the required bandwidth to attain low phase shift on higher frequencies. The Op Amps with current feedback have larger bandwidth in comparison to the voltage feedback Op Amps. However there remains a difficulty in practical usage of these due to their sensitivity of the feedback capacitance.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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